

EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AT THE NEW QUALITY LEVEL OF SOCIETY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8124162>

Abstract: In the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, the scientific considerations on bringing the education system to a new level of quality, development of society through science and innovation are presented. Also, the fact that changes and innovations are increasing in all areas is scientifically based on the fact that carrying out modernization processes in the field of education is an important factor of social development.

Key words: education, innovation, non-state education system, professional education, social development, action strategy

The social development of the society is determined by the standard of living of the population, well-being, lifestyle and economic stability of the state. Today, when our country has entered a new period of its development, large-scale changes are being implemented in all areas based on the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. He emphasized that the tasks of education of the government of the republic "...first of all, it is inextricably linked with the development of the field of science and education, with our ability to compete on a global scale in this regard"[1]. Therefore, the main task is to improve the living standards and financial support of people in Uzbekistan, and to reform the education system by increasing the number of new enterprises and jobs. Changing people's knowledge, worldview, way of thinking, educating a generation of potential personnel is also a component of it. After all, education as a guarantee of youth development is "a rational solution to solving important problems of society"[2].

The head of our state, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, in the formation of the modern education system in our country, said that "implementation of the multifaceted and complex tasks that we have set before ourselves will be carried out by modern and creative thinking, capable of taking responsibility in any situation, enthusiastic, high intellectual potential, patriotic young personnel intended to entrust important tasks in the management of the state and society"[3]. It is important that society's development and educational problems are determined by the participation of potential and competitive personnel in management, and the ability to positively solve the situation by understanding the problems of modern education. We can create a revolution and a great change by forming a scientific elite of leading intellectual youth, considering that education determines the progress and decline of societies. In this sense, we believe that education is the discovery of human personality, the realization of the national identity of young people, the perception of existence, and the factor of the well-being of society. We explain our opinion by the fact that education is a part of the universal human value, the main passion of the individual is considered a natural historical phenomenon formed by national genetics. That is why "systematic work is being carried out in the directions of strengthening the protection of the socio-economic interests of young people,

increasing their socio-political activity and legal culture, realizing the national identity, and forming a high level of spirituality"[4]. The government of Uzbekistan takes into account that this problem and its solution have a serious impact on the state and non-state education system, the protection of educational interests with the active participation of the public, and the mood and social goals of young people. This, in turn, shows that one of the important tasks is to determine the factors of formation of social development of education, philosophical justification of the social necessity of professional education with the problems of national development.

If education is a factor that creates social development, then social development is a criterion of the level of professionalism of education. So, social development and education are mutually developing, complementary and mutually supportive processes. The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev supported the initiative of "Kazakhstan leader Nursultan Nazarboev to achieve sustainable and inclusive economic development, to organize integration of infrastructures between Muslim countries aimed at strengthening mutually beneficial cooperation" [5].

The gradual improvement of social development and the analysis of the laws of the development of the society allows to control the evolution of the educational system. Because in the principle of historicity, it is possible to observe the interrelationship between education and the development of societies. If the strict and closed system of education is an important component of the state system of a particular country, it is also reflected in the quality indicator of human life, development and individual well-being index at the beginning of the new century. As a result of these works, "the rapid development of education has turned it into one of the important factors of human and society development" [6], and this leads to social development.

From the second half of the last century, international organizations started the process of regulating the education system and developing the legal basis of education in the whole world. In particular, the establishment of a separate department aimed at the development of science, education and social life by the UN was one of the important steps. The "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" adopted by the UN established the right of every person to education. As a result, the right to education was guaranteed throughout the world, and the right to education was made a constitutional right in every independent country. It began to appear that education is the basis of the development of society, the factor that moves it and takes it to great heights. Therefore, any discrimination in the field of education was considered a violation of human rights.

Education develops a social outlook in the society, increases the level of literacy of people, reduces unemployment and reduces the level of neediness of the population. In general, the educational level of the society is the basis of social development, the country with high literacy will have relatively wider opportunities in terms of production and population employment. In such countries, as a rule, there is a low level of unemployment and the number of people who are able to work go to other countries in search of work. It is easier for an educated person to find a job than an uneducated person. In all countries, the unemployment rate is always high among the population with little or no education"[7]. Therefore, unemployment in the labor market or insufficient salary for work is determined by the applicant's education and professional ability, and all social problems are explained by ignorance and low level of education.

Education is reflected in health care, longevity, access to health care, healthy lifestyles and culture. Quality education shapes the effectiveness of medicine and affects the long and healthy life of the population. As a result, the level of health of the population has increased, and the longevity of the population in the country - 67 years for men and 73 years for women - is considered a positive indicator in international indices" [8]. Therefore, ensuring social progress, bringing the society to a new stage of development requires professional medical services as well as the health of the population.

If we look at history, many countries have achieved economic development and achievement of high goals by supporting education, science, and paying special attention to them. In this sense, we are researcher M. We would like to quote Temirova's opinion that "... our forefathers considered knowledge, education and upbringing to be the most important condition and guarantee of human perfection and development of the nation, which is a priceless wealth from time immemorial."

In the long-term trends of the country's economic development, the analysis of increasing the level of education is inextricably linked, and the indices of the level of education are shown in the periodic trend. In the last century, the country could be temporarily rich due to colonialism and plundering wars. So, if the state needs factors such as natural resources and agriculture as the basis for being temporarily rich and economically developed, quality education, science, and innovation are necessary for the foundation of sustainable economic development. Therefore, "today, brutal competition on the world scale is becoming more and more intense. In such a complex environment, we support the idea of connecting parents' participation in education with a "happy future" for the wide introduction of modern science and innovation achievements[9].

In some cases, scientists relied on the increase in the price of the country's cashed natural resources and concluded that "in the conditions of modern globalization and growing international competition, the wealth that has come from the sale of raw materials will not last long if it is not supported by the increasing level of education of the population and the effective channeling of the acquired knowledge into the economy [10]]. Therefore, the increase in the level of knowledge of the society through education has a significant impact on their lifestyle and cultural life. We believe that this situation depends in many ways on the personnel training system of social development in the development of civil society.

Today, the introduction of new technologies, the production of modern goods, and the growth of communication skills create conditions for the disappearance or change of some types of work. In this regard, the need to constantly improve the professional competences of employees requires their professionalization to grow. Because in the labor process (30-40 years old) it is not possible to use only the stock of knowledge based on studying at a college or university. After all, "Intellectual development of society is the basis of social development. We agree with the views that without it, it is impossible to achieve scientific and technical progress, it is impossible to make discoveries that ensure the stable life of society in the global interest of man [11]. Therefore, the process of professional education is longer in time and covers various stages of professional development, as well as the content of educational activities is broader, including the creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions for training personnel within the organization, various forms of skill development and retraining. Also, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, social development depends on the work of the governing bodies on the basis of open, fair and legal principles.

Scientists have recognized that for many years there have been "extremely urgent, urgent tasks related to the renewal and modernization of Uzbekistan, the liberalization of all aspects of our society, the further improvement of the standard of living and the quality of life of our people, and the raising of the country's reputation in the international arena" [12]. At the same time, modernization of the activities of other state bodies and administrative agencies is an important factor in the development of society. The second aspect of the problem, the process of globalization and internationalization of economic relations can be explained by the activities of joint ventures with the participation of foreign capital. At the same time, high-level competition between countries is increasing, and those who conduct long-term and continuous education programs are leading the competition. This situation requires meeting the requirements of the world market by training highly qualified personnel and ensuring labor productivity. Historical experience shows that the development of mankind has been "searching for the possibilities of a prosperous life and trying to use them effectively." He went through a complex period from the use of simple labor tools to the creation of high-tech equipment and processes at the level of today's modern demand and effective use of them to ensure his well-being" [13]. As a result of these processes, human consciousness developed, and this brought social development to its present form.

We bear in mind that employment changes in manufacturing and business sectors, the constantly changing dynamics of vocational training of workers in the national economy, the potential of skilled workers in the labor market and significant demographic growth are also a third factor.

At the same time, commercial organizations in Uzbekistan have overcome the difficulties of their formation stage, entered the stage of stabilization and acquired a sufficiently high level of human capital. Since the stability of development is often in conflict with the dynamics of the market, when a fundamental change in the development and operation of the organization is necessary, in accordance with the changed market conditions, corporate training is urgently needed.

In the process of education, the basic meaning and the necessity of the introduced changes are communicated to the employees, the essence of which is to achieve support for the organization's innovative policy, and to overcome the resistance of ordinary employees to innovations. This corresponds to the changed approaches in the strategic management of the organization, which is considered to be real and effective only if the development strategy is the work of not only the company's management, but also the employees of the entire organization. After all, it is no secret that "today, perfect mastery of modern science and high technologies is becoming a decisive condition for the development of any state and society. With a deep understanding of this fact, we are mobilizing all the forces and opportunities for our modern generation to grow up both physically and spiritually" [14]. As a result of these works, it is necessary to have effective education and the formation of a high level of social well-being.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the main requirements and tasks for education can be grouped into a number of groups:

First of all, personnel training in industrialized countries is based on a stable system of company-employee relations, competitiveness, which ensures the company's success. In the 50s of the 20th century, representatives of Japanese industrial management realized that the

main asset of the company is people. In the 70s of the 20th century, the concept of continuous education of developed countries was developed, and until now it has been recognized that personnel qualifications are an effective solution to the problem of compliance with the dynamic requirements of technical development. Annually spending two to five percent of the budget of large Western corporations on training and professional development of employees, while in the United States training costs exceed \$ 200 billion, Canada allocates an average of \$ 500 per employee to the sector. For example, Motorola estimates that every dollar spent on education generates \$33 in benefits. Analogous ideas and information are also found in scientific articles [15].

At the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, creating a promising education system, emphasizing quality and competitiveness in personnel training, forming the principles of legality, fairness, and openness in management is an important factor in achieving social development. According to the opinions of Professor Sadulla Otamuratov about the possibilities of developing science, technology and technology independently of developing and underdeveloped countries, the following can be distinguished:

First of all, science, technology, and technological achievements introduced by developed countries are cheap. Because they do not have enough funds for development at the level of today's development requirements. Moreover, there is a need to form intellectuals at the level of modern requirements. But it is cheaper to buy ready-made than to spend a lot of money on their formation.

Second, times are changing at an unprecedented rate, and development is accelerating accordingly, and highly developed countries are leading this process. It cannot be ignored. Because time is merciless, there is no way to stop it. This forces developing and underdeveloped countries and the nations living in them to waste time. After all, failure to take into account the current processes and the acceleration of development will lead to the occurrence of a negative situation in the life of citizens in these countries and, ultimately, to chaos[16]. Therefore, in order for Uzbekistan to gain time as a developing country and become one of the developed countries in terms of social development, educational reform is very necessary.

In general, all countries in the world strive for development. Are there criteria for measuring developed and backward countries? For some countries, development is the acquisition of wealth, or for other countries, development is an important task of ensuring people's well-being, creating suitable conditions for freedom and social protection in society, and creating conditions for people to work comfortably.

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